

POLYSEMY OF VERBS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the significant role of polysemy in the Uzbek language. The richness of the language is measured not only by words and phrases, but also by the lexical meanings of words. Therefore, the multiplicity of meanings of words - polysemy - has its place in the richness of the language.

In our linguistics, a lot of work has been done to study polysemy in comparison with its cognates and to determine its scope. It is also appropriate to note the works of French, German, English, Czech, Russian and Uzbek linguists who have written about this. Although these scientific works are not in the form of special monographs or important articles dedicated to polysemy and its cognates, they contain valuable ideas that can include subtle features that distinguish polysemy from cognates. However, these works distinguish polysemy only from some cognates. They also explain the difference between polysemy and homonymy and the fact that the meanings of words in a phrase are irrelevant for the polysemantic word structure. We will dwell on these works in turn.

Also, the number of lexical meanings that make up the semantic structure of a given polysemantic word does not necessarily correspond to the semantic-content value noted in the dictionary article. Because the lexicographic level does not deny the inclusion of other meanings in the lexical meaning of a word in the dictionary article. Many phenomena of the language are confused with polysemy. The accompanying phenomena that cause confusion with polysemy are mainly the following: 1) conversion, 2) generalization, 3) phrase. The development of lexical meanings as a result of subordination can lead to a breakdown in the connection between the meanings of polysemantic words. As is known, the development of lexical meanings as a result of subordination causes the emergence of polysemantic words.

For example, let's pay attention to the development of meaning in the word fist. Its first meaning is "the state of the fingers of the hand closed." The lexical meaning expressing "the blow of the fist" is a transitive meaning formed as a result of this subordination. We give examples for the main and transitive meanings.

To fabricate is the accusative of the verb to fabricate. In the meaning of the verb to fabricate, the transitive meaning of "to weave lies" was formed by metonymy. When this meaning became the main meaning for the transitive meaning, the verb corresponding to this

meaning was in the form of the accusative, as noted above. However, the transitive meaning formed from it. is devoid of accusative in relation to the laws of the language. The transitive meaning of "to weave a lie", which is the result of the semantic development of the verb to weave, has become an independent meaning due to the lack of a meaning that is inherently connected to the genetic meaning of this verb and does not correspond to the grammatical form.

Takilmok is the transitive relation of the verb to weave. The transitive meaning of "to try to pass" was formed metaphorically from the disappeared meaning of the verb to weave. When this meaning became the basis for the transitive meaning, the verb corresponding to this meaning, as noted above, was in the transitive relation. However, the transitive meaning formed from it does not have the transitive relation. Moreover, the meaning that gave rise to this meaning has gone beyond the scope of application. The transitive meaning of "to try to pass", which is the result of the semantic development of the verb to weave, has become an independent meaning due to the lack of a connecting meaning to the semantic meaning of this verb and does not correspond to the grammatical form.

Polysemy is the fact that a word has more than one lexical meaning. Thus, polysemy is measured by the number of lexical meanings in a word. This also occurs when a word has a transliterated meaning.

In short, the lexical meanings that are part of the structure of a polysemantic word are expressed only in the word itself. The meaning that is common to the entire compound does not play a role in the fact that one of the components of this compound is a polysemantic word.

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